

JOINT SERVICES AUTOMATIC TEST PROGRAM — REVISITED

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ABSTRACT

Early in 1978, the Joint Logistic Commanders established a Panel on Automatic Testing. The Panel developed a Study Plan, which defines 20 tasks to be accomplished in Automatic Testing by the Services.

Subpanels covering Management, Acquisition Support, and Testing Technology are operating and have defined over 100 subtasks to be performed. Progress will be monitored by a Management Information System. Results of the Industry/Joint Services Automatic Test Project will play an important part in this program.

INTRODUCTION

At last November's AUTOTESTCON, CAPT H. M. Walker of the Naval Material Command's Test and Monitoring Systems Program Office, summarized the interests, effort, and results of the Joint Service Steering Committee for Automatic Testing which led to the formalization of the Industry/Joint Services Automatic Test Project. The purpose of that organization was to plan, coordinate, and combine, in an efficient manner, the many common efforts to be accomplished.

When the five Industry Associations, represented in the Industry Ad Hoc Automatic Test Equipment Project for the Navy, agreed to expand the study to include the three Services, it became appropriate for the Services to prepare an overall automatic test equipment management plan covering management, acquisition support, and testing technology (R&D). The plan was prepared and briefed to the Joint Logistic Commanders (JLC), a group of four Four-star officers respectively commanding the Department of the Army Readiness Command (DARCOM), the Naval Material Command (NMC), the Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC), and the Air Force Systems Command (AFSC). Recognizing the anticipated return from a Joint Service effort in this vital area, the JLC established a Panel on Automatic Testing to coordinate and focus the individual and collective Service automatic testing efforts.

THE PANEL AND ITS WORK

The Panel was chartered by the JLC on 22 March 1978. The mission of the Panel is to:

- a. Develop methods of reducing hardware, software, and manpower costs associated with Automatic Testing for support of Weapon Systems.
- b. Devise policies, plans, and procedures in the use of automatic testing hardware and software to improve operational readiness of Weapon Systems.
- c. Facilitate exchange among the Services and OSD of technical, managerial, and operational information on automatic testing hardware and software as it applies to the support of Weapon Systems.

At the first Panel meeting, held in April, the Members elected a Chairman and three Subpanels were formed to coordinate effort in Management, Acquisition Support, and Testing Technology. Panel constituents are shown in Figure 1. Each of the Commands has selected and is represented by a Member of the Panel and an Alternate Member. This group represents the continuing cooperative effort initiated early in 1977 to work with the Industry/Joint Services Automatic Test Project. The Marine Corps and the Defense Logistics Agency Associate Members round out the Panel. Subpanel Members are shown in Figure 2. These people will be responsible for describing, in detail, subtasks to be performed and they will provide direct monitoring of progress, as discussed later.

A Study Plan was written whose scope considers all aspects of Automatic Testing (i.e., on-line testing (including built-in-test), off-line testing, and Weapon System testability). The tasks include efforts to:

- a. Generate policies and procedures which can be applied DoD-wide or Service-wide to optimize definition, application, and support of automatic testing hardware and software in the system acquisition management process.

<u>MEMBERS</u>	<u>ALTERNATES</u>
G. W. NEUMANN, NAVMAT, CHAIRMAN	CAPT H. M. WALKER, NAVMAT
LCOL L. MURRAY, DARCOM	COL E. THOMPSON, DARCOM
LCOL F. ZEMLICKA, AFLC	A. BACA, AFLC
C. WALKER, AFSC	MAJ M. ANDERSON, AFSC
	O. SEPP, ASD
 <u>ASSOCIATES</u>	
CAPT R. SHERMAN, USMC	
G. SCHIEFFELIN, DLA	

Figure 1. JLC Panel Membership.

<u>MANAGEMENT</u>	
J. JOHNSON, SA-ALC, CHAIRMAN	
P. GROSS, NAVMAT	
R. WILSON, ARMY	
LCOL K. WILKINSON, ASD	
 <u>ACQUISITION SUPPORT</u>	
M. BENANTI, CORADCOM, CHAIRMAN	
G. NEUMANN, NAVMAT	
J. DEWEY, AFLC	
L. JEPSON, SAMSO	
MAJ M. ANDERSON, AFSC	
 <u>TESTING TECHNOLOGY</u>	
F. MICKA, ASD, CHAIRMAN	
M. NUNN, NOSC	
M. TENZER, CORADCOM	
W. BOLIN, WR-ALC	
R. WINGENTER, SA-ALC	
J. STOUT, ASD	

Figure 2. JLC Subpanel Membership.

- b. Develop system engineering and logistics tools, techniques, and guidelines which will enhance the application of automatic testing in the design and support of Weapon Systems and subsystems.
- c. Coordinate R&D planning and execution in testing technology and associated software (all RDT&E categories) to minimize duplication of effort and produce a coherent program directed toward achieving common testing technology objectives.

The final Study Plan was completed by the Panel on 31 August 1978. Representing substantial coordination among the various Commands, the Plan contains 110

subtasks classified under 20 tasks. Figure 3 provides a listing of these tasks, showing the categorization under each Subpanel. The five Management tasks are expected to develop management policies, procedures, guidance, and controls necessary for Service Program Managers to integrate Automatic Testing elements into Weapon Systems development and acquisition phases in an effective and timely manner. The tasks will develop specific language in directives and instructions for including Automatic Testing concepts and equipment in Weapon Systems acquisition. Also, Services will define structures for organizational visibility of Automatic Testing elements and provide for personnel career guidance. Control and guidance will be developed to assist managers in delineating acquisition interfaces among Automatic Test Equipment, Automatic Data Processing Equipment, and Weapon Systems hardware and software.

<u>MANAGEMENT</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • POLICY AND PROCEDURE • DOCUMENTATION • CAREER GUIDANCE • ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE • WEAPON SYSTEM/AT/ADPE COMPUTER ACQUISITION INTERFACES
<u>ACQUISITION SUPPORT</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TERMINOLOGY AND DATA EXCHANGE • TESTABILITY GUIDELINES • LOGISTICS • TEST PROGRAM SETS AND RELATED SOFTWARE • HARDWARE INTERFACE • EDUCATION AND TRAINING • TESTING REQUIREMENTS • AT ACQUISITION
<u>TESTING TECHNOLOGY</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOFTWARE • AUTOMATIC TEST GENERATION • DESIGN FOR TESTABILITY • MACHINERY TESTING • NEW TECHNOLOGY • EDUCATION, TRAINING AND MANAGEMENT AIDS • ADVANCED ATE CONCEPTS

Figure 3. Study Plan Tasks.

Eight tasks have been defined by the Acquisition Support Subpanel. These tasks will be concerned with developing tools necessary to integrate Automatic Testing elements into Weapon Systems acquisitions. The tasks include improving communications through update of the Automatic Testing terminology standard (MIL-STD-1309), development of a DoD/Service-wide information exchange system and an Automatic Testing Newsletter. Built-in-Test (BIT) and Testability Design Guides will be developed and published. By integrating Systems Engineering and Logistics modeling and analysis techniques, an effort will be made to determine the impact of Automatic Testing functions on Weapon Systems in such areas as life cycle costs, performance tradeoffs, and support requirements. By adopting and maintaining a DoD standard test language and developing specialized software acquisition guides, such acquisition will be substantially simplified and made more efficient. Specifications for controlling on- and off-line testing interfaces will be developed. Acquisition managers

training programs will be planned and implemented in a series of courses. A standard for Test Requirements Documents (TRD) and an AT Acquisition Guide will be published.

The Testing Technology tasks, of which seven have been defined, are intended to assist in establishing research, development, test and evaluation (RDT&E) programs required to maintain and improve Automatic Testing state-of-the-art. Automatic Testing software development will be enhanced through development of tools, languages, and techniques, and through identification of software drivers. Analog and digital automatic test generators will be evaluated and developed. BIT and Design for Testability concepts and techniques will be developed and formalized. Monitoring, fault detection, and fault isolation methods for nonelectronic equipment and devices will be developed. Monitoring and testing techniques for devices and equipment utilizing new technologies will be investigated. Training aids for Automatic Testing operating and maintenance personnel will be developed. Families of Automatic Test Equipment will be developed to reduce or eliminate duplication and proliferation.

To implement specific subtasks, the Subpanel Members detail the approach to be applied, establish milestones, and estimate the required funds and manpower. The task approach plan is submitted to the Panel for review and approval. Based on expertise, available funding, and required schedule, selection of a designated Command to implement the effort will be made. The Plan is then forwarded to the selected lead Command who will be responsible for accepting the task, and accomplishment and coordination of the effort. The Subpanel will monitor progress and report to the Panel. Periodic progress reviews will be presented to the JLC by the Panel.

A Management Information System (MIS) will be used to provide real-time status on tasks and subtasks, track milestones, and provide a library of inputs and outputs for each task. An annual Joint Service AT Review is planned to provide inter-Service communication of accomplishments and future plans. Figure 4 shows the impact of the MIS.

Close contact with other JLC groups, and specifically with the Industry/Joint Services AT Project, will continue. When results and recommendations from the Industry effort are hardened, the JLC Panel will review them for applicability to the Study Plan and integrate them into the first revision of the Plan, scheduled for mid-1979. Many of the military advisors on the Industry Project are also contributing to the Panel's deliberations. In any event, the Study Plan will be a dynamic document. It will be reviewed annually to consider additions, deletions, and changes in emphasis of tasks, as appropriate. The first revision changes will be summarized and reported at the annual Joint Services AT review.

Figure 4. Management Information System.

Persons wishing to obtain a copy of the current issue of the Study Plan may write to:

DEPARTMENT OF THE NAVY
HEADQUARTERS, NAVAL MATERIAL COMMAND
ATTN: CODE MAT 04T
WASHINGTON, D.C. 20360

A number of activities are already being pursued. A few are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Current Joint Services Activities

The Navy's Automatic Testing Acquisition Managers course has been expanded to have a Joint Service flavor and presented to Army and Air Force people. The Air Force Aeronautical Systems Division has been surveying Support Equipment Data Banks available in all the Services in order to determine if a Joint Service system of data retrieval can be accomplished. Both the Army and Navy are participating, by invitation, in the Air Force Systems Command's Modular Automatic Test Equipment program (MATE). The initial segment was awarded on 30 June. The Army and Navy have assigned liaison personnel to provide close communications as the program develops. The morning session on Wednesday provided some details on the objectives of the MATE program and the approaches being taken by the two contractors of the initial segment, Sperry and Westinghouse.

SUMMARY

The JLC Panel on Automatic Testing has become the central focus for military considerations in the automatic testing field. The Panel has been officially chartered and its Study Plan approved. Implementation is going forward.